

MIMS 2.1.1-2 : Aether, Business & Analytics

With a short reflection upon the philosophies of Ayn Rand and the concepts of Fortune as it relates to the Aether

A SPACERS™ paper¹ under AIM™ standards

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Best viewed at: <https://bit.ly/37vjrdF>

ABSTRACT

Ayn Rand believed that business was a natural, even spiritual outflow of mankind's creative genius, and as such was a holy act, perhaps even holier than the "mystics" of religious cults. Nevertheless, from an EPEMC perspective, and in particular a MIMS hypothesis, the author wishes to explore the population of material wealth, from atomic signals and in particular the proper use of data analytics, with a special attention drawn to the unique interactions of the Force, Aether, and Numbers (*F, A, and N* powers). Is there something about business which is a) bolstered by the PEM force, and b) keeps mankind behaving in a *less sinful* manner? Are these related to the concepts of fortune (luck and/or wealth)? Will the proper motivation of business lead towards a new space race which will lift all of mankind out of poverty and alleviate the threat of Class 7+ cataclysms?

Keywords: MIMS - space - terraform - strategy - business - Aether - luck - fortune

¹ SPACERS is a secret acronym, but suffice it to say business strategy is one of the core aspects to the business, as is analytics.

Introduction: What's in an Aether?

Of all the 5 (or 6) powers from Figure 3 of the first MIMS paper, here reproduced², none are so difficult to pin down as the Aether. In a previous EPEMC paper the author introduced the ideas of the plasma-electromagnetic sky³ and that the shells of Earth and Heaven were actually nothing more than charge distribution layers. Separately, in medical research, the concept of Charge Distribution Networks as channels to propagate health or disease signals in the body⁴, was derived first from observation about Chinese Medicine, and clinical results, particularly with Electric Fields⁵, and then from the PEMS concepts. The result was the idea of a cosmology of continuous recirculation of charge, with:

1. The "Sea of Charge" (cosmic 'dust' and plasma) being the Aether itself, since EMF needs no other medium to propagate itself.

Figure 1 - The "Big G" in EPEMC; author

2. The network constantly rearranging and inducing new fields both magnetic and electrical constituting a "Cosmic Rearrangement Hypothesis" (CRH)
3. This necessitated a new form of entropy "Two Way Entropy" or "Dual Direction Entropy" in which the author postulated a "spongy counter space" that absorbs ambient energy out of the visible space and matter, and then it matriculates towards the plasmoids (AGN, Quasars, pulsars, magnetars, etc.) and stars for gathering and then re-immersion into the space. The details of 2WE or DDE are to be discussed in a separate EPEMC paper.

² Please note that the L power can be listed as Consciousness (C power) if one wants a more psychological approach. However, in EPEMC, there is no shyness regarding mankind's factual historical connection to a Creator God - whatever its form - and the Lord was a main contributor to human knowledge and power. It may be that - relative to the Lord's perspective - there is no factual difference. It may also be that Consciousness is an emergent property of the interaction of the other "yang elements" such as the PEMF and UAF, and the Laws of Nature (P power), in which case it's all redundant anyhow. See I Ching hexagram #1 - Ch'ien - The Creative for diagram and remarks from the ancients about this issue. Note that the Ch'ien is homophonic to Tian - Heaven - and is also a plasmaglyph for the Above God - Shang Di.

https://www.academia.edu/38590072/Shang_Di_Heaven_and_Dao

3

https://www.academia.edu/36753643/Our_Plasma_Electromagnetic_Sky_Application_of_Hollow_Expanding_Growing_Electromagnetic_Earth_Hypothesis_with_particular_respect_to_the_Earths_Atmosphere_starting_from_the_Lithosphere_and_ascending_Altitude

4

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/330117614_Charge_Distribution_Networks_CDN_as_Meridians_Utilizing_conductivity_as_replacement_structure_for_meridians_comparison_with_neural_muscular_and_fascial_models

5

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/328697566_Clinical_Electric_Field_Measurements_In_situ_pre_and_post_treatment_measurement_data_with_weather_and_space-weather_lunar_and_solar_data_with_self-reported_pain_and_significance_scales_in_three_phases

The result is a is much more concrete, mysterious than current like Stringy Branes⁶, Space-time. On the first measurable, and so are a macro and micro scale. contains the unborn should work-ums” that inventions and unknown not much clearer than the the spongy counter space

view of the Aether which and yet far more Standard Model ideas Quantum Foam⁷, or hand charges are the motions of matter on However, how this data concepts and “how it constitute future (as of yet) technologies is anatomy and physics of (SCS) itself.

Figure 2 - The Universe “forming” according to Standard Model... useful in seeing the emerging network filamentation of structure⁸. Credit: NASA

So how do things move from the SCS and what could be termed “full potential” into the subatomic and atomic, thence to the energy flow we are familiar with in the Laws of Life⁹, and in particular how we experience it on Earth in the PEMS+HEGEME¹⁰ interactive shells? From there, how do they go from Potential to the Probability-Possibility Cloud (PPPC), and from there become compressed through an Actualization Process (AP) into the 3 dimensional array? Disregarding if the data is holographic or not, there is some motion from the PPPC into reification through this AP. At the end of which, some people have “all the luck” some have bad luck or what the Chinese better term “misfortune” whereas (as discussed in MIMS 2.0) others are able to take future data and make it “now” and become sensationally rich¹¹. Not just commonly fortunate, either, but immortalized even. They are able to make fuller use of the PEMF¹² than almost anyone else, and thereby funnel more reality out of the PPPC than others. Some are so successful (like Sir Isaac Newton) that they even manage to funnel more *fantasy* out of the PPPC and as noted previously, more bad ideas = more good ideas¹³.

⁶ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Brane>

⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Quantum_foam

⁸ What the Chinese term the “wood phase” of energy, which is the Force (F power) in the Big G.

⁹

https://www.academia.edu/37439506/Magnetic_Universe_Theory_A_Top_Down_Review_of_Phases_of_Magnetic_Theory_Development_with_accompanying_historiography_and_comparison_with_Unified_Aether_Field_Theories_including_EPEMC pp. 134

¹⁰ Plasma Electromagnetic Sky & “Hollow” Expanding-Growing Electromagnetic Earth; see https://www.academia.edu/36753643/Our_Plasma_Electromagnetic_Sky_Application_of_Hollow_Expanding_Growing_Electromagnetic_Earth_Hypothesis_with_particular_respect_to_the_Earths_Atmosphere_starting_from_the_Lithosphere_and_ascending_Altitude

¹¹ https://www.academia.edu/50804855/MIMS_2_Applications_discussions

¹² Please remember that the PEMF = F power (the Force).

¹³ Ibid. pp. 14

Figure 3 - "Triple plane" - an early pre-EPEMC MIMS model describing the interaction of the "mental plane" (cycle of mind) with the PPC, and parallel realities in a 3 phase interactive motion; credit: author

Does our diagram account for this? Something moving from the "above position" and unseen stratum, to the created or *actualized* "below position" where it is seen. Their energy is somehow converted from the etheric to the atomic, and these atoms are now interacting in generally predictable manners. Before, the Aether - in the form of this PPC - was relatively unpredictable, amorphous, ambiguous even. But now it is essentially *crystallized* into a matrix of behavior. Upon this fact rests our knowledge of chemistry, finance, physics, and a number of other important human tools and powers which run our society.

We see that it is clearly the *P* power which mediates this behavior... determining what matter and energy *do* as they interact with each other, and how these can be controlled by either the *L* or *N* powers on either side of the Principles of Physics (Laws of Nature). But, again, the exact means of how this is controlled by "Heaven's Will" in the Aether is still quite unknown¹⁴. This is important for three reasons:

¹⁴ In quantum physics there are 4 solutions to causality, and this means, ultimately, we really don't know how it all works. The Chinese, also, did not have a good solution so they came down to: Karma, Fate, Destiny, Luck, and Chaos. Karma is causality or the "law of sowing and reaping" as in the Bible. Fate is after "it is written" whereas Destiny unfolds. Luck is dependent on your astrology - which the Chinese rely on time for, rather than planets - and Chaos is the literal jiggle of the unknown in the PPC.

1. The Aether corresponds to Water phase, which controls Fire (consciousness or *L* power), but is controlled by the Earth phase (Principles)
2. Via the concept of fluids/flux the water is related to the wind and in the 8 Principles, Wind trigram corresponds to flux itself, aka Evolution, aka the Changes themselves.^{15 16}
3. Wood and wind correspond, and water is the “mother” of wood phase, so we see that The Changes (the cosmic rearrangement) is directly related to the *F* power - the Plasma-electromagnetic Unified Aether Force¹⁷ - and this will, of course, mean that changes to the Sea of Charge and its induced fields - force free or otherwise - will mean changes to the available aether and therefore “fortunes”.

These are basic interactions deduced from the diagram of Figure 1, but also from observations in nature itself (empiricism).

Please note that the proper method to attract Aether in the body is through the “crown chakra” of the top of the head where the toroidal field connects, and that this aether is considered a form of Qi (Chinese charge?) that comes from Heaven itself - the creative field. More on this subject is covered in a pre-EPEMC paper by the author¹⁸. However, from here on out we cannot discuss the CDNs and chakras in more depth, it will be assumed that the reader understands that all Luck and Fortune comes from the attraction of this “moral force” (Te¹⁹) and capture in the heart’s electrodynamic; see: the Nei Yeh for more ancient information on this dynamic.²⁰

MIMS 2.1.1 - Capitalism as a Flow

In order to discuss the purpose - or indeed holiness - of business, and the “immutable dynamics of business flow”²¹ one must and needs to discuss capital, capitalism, and the obviously improved conditions in

¹⁵

https://www.academia.edu/50804985/Trigram_Law_Energy_Spirit_Substance_Mental_Physical_Xie_Mental_Xie_Spiritual_Xie_Fibonacci

¹⁶ https://www.academia.edu/50804995/Bagua_Dharma_Lectures_1_and_2

¹⁷ “Mag Universe” paper, Ibid. pp1, 22

¹⁸ https://www.academia.edu/8547496/Scalar_Magnetic_Waves_and_Qi_a_first_draft_of_a_hypothesis

¹⁹ Please note that Te 德 means “inner power” [dynamo] that connects the human to Tao 道 (Dao)... the Force... and that Te is itself a well described plasmascript. See the Sumo Paper for details,

https://www.academia.edu/38268897/Sumo_Ancient_Ritual_to_the_Thunder_God pp 10

²⁰ <https://bit.ly/3xIjBhS>

²¹ “Jensen: You have meddled with the primal forces of nature, Mr. Beale, and I won't have it!! Is that clear?! You think you've merely stopped a business deal. That is not the case. The Arabs have taken billions of dollars out of this country, and now they must put it back! It is ebb and flow, tidal gravity! It is ecological balance! You are an old man who thinks in terms of nations and peoples. There are no nations. There are no peoples. There are no Russians. There are no Arabs. There are no third worlds. There is no West. There is only one holistic system of systems, one vast and immane, interwoven, interacting, multivariate, multinational dominion of dollars. Petro-dollars, electro-dollars, multi-dollars, reichsmarks, rurs, rubles, pounds, and shekels. It is the international system of currency which determines the totality of life on this planet. That is the natural order of things today. That is the atomic and subatomic and galactic structure of things today! And YOU have meddled with the primal forces of nature, and YOU WILL ATONE!

Am I getting through to you, Mr. Beale?

which this pre-Industrial Revolution, pre-PEM conceptualization, arose. It arose, primarily, out of the Age of Exploration under Queen Elizabeth I, who was the first modern historical crown power to guarantee the losses on the exploration of the world's first corporation: the Dutch East Indies Company²². By doing so, business was able to stretch further than any merchant ever had, and with more leverage. It also marked the actualization of the writing on the wall, so to speak, that had been the Magna Carta²³... to the end of Divine Right to Rule²⁴. Instead, business would become the order of the day, and it has remained so ever since.

What is capitalism? It is the decentralization of exchange, the removal of third parties, between the capital exchanges of goods and services of two or more parties. It represents, in essence, a vast exponential jump in currency-exchange data-rate, by removing impedance in the circuit of business²⁵. Whereas before under mercantilism and feudalism there was a hum-drum rate of exchange of data, information, and capital (money), capitalism freed this up for massive increase. It created, as a proxy, a greater chance for greed, corruption, abuse (cons and scams, mostly), but it also freed up market forces and a whole new set of P powers based on laws of economics that had not been previously understood, and which had at times directly affected humanity greatly. One such example is the Law of Supply, which because of the amount of Spanish gold taken from the colonies had mysteriously led to the collapse of the Spanish Empire²⁶. This seemed, at the time, counter-intuitive.

By engaging in free market capitalism, the *N* power unleashed upon humanity rapid growth of exchanges in ideas, both good (Renaissance and Industrial Revolution, and Science) and bad (religious cultism and Socialism, and imperialism, etc.), which led one and all to the Great Enlightenment, and the

You get up on your little twenty-one inch screen and howl about America and democracy. There is no America. There is no democracy. There is only IBM and ITT and AT&T and DuPont, Dow, Union Carbide, and Exxon. Those are the nations of the world today.

What do you think the Russians talk about in their councils of state -- Karl Marx? They get out their linear programming charts, statistical decision theories, minimax solutions, and compute the price-cost probabilities of their transactions and investments, just like we do.

We no longer live in a world of nations and ideologies, Mr. Beale. The world is a college of corporations, inexorably determined by the immutable bylaws of business. The world is a business, Mr. Beale. It has been since man crawled out of the slime. And our children will live, Mr. Beale, to see that perfect world in which there's no war or famine, oppression or brutality -- one vast and ecumenical holding company, for whom all men will work to serve a common profit, in which all men will hold a share of stock, all necessities provided, all anxieties tranquilized, all boredom amused. And I have chosen you, Mr. Beale, to preach this evangel."

<https://www.americanrhetoric.com/MovieSpeeches/moviespeechnetwork4.html>

²² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Dutch_East_India_Company ; but for a better treatment the author recommends "Grunch of Giants," by Buckminster Fuller

²³ <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Magna-Carta>

²⁴

https://www.academia.edu/38993303/Caer_Melyn_Camelot_Cosmic_Hillfort_of_the_King_The_Yellow_Hill_fort_as_a_Cosmic_Hill_or_mountain_motif_and_symbol_of_a_Kings_authority

²⁵ If one will recall from the first MIMS paper, the power in a business is inverted, but as in physics power is directly relational to the inversion of impedance, or directly proportional to conductance.

https://www.academia.edu/50300514/On_the_Membranous_Interface_of_the_Material_and_the_Spiritual_from_an_EPEMC_perspective_and_Dual_Double_Layer_Economics_a_proposed_test_of_EPEMCs_metallic_properties_tensile_strength_malleability_durability pp. 23

²⁶

<https://history.stackexchange.com/questions/9060/how-did-the-gold-of-the-new-world-cause-the-spanish-empire-to-collapse>

release of mankind from poverty. Prior to 1850 almost the entire world subsisted on around \$1 per day. Since then, the world's average income per person has steadily increased... even with world wars, etc.²⁷

Why does throughput increase in capitalism and increase the power of the Force to affect changes in people's lives? It literally increases the interaction rate between the 5 powers, and humanity! On top of this, there appears to be an exponential increase (as well) in ideas, and in the PPC aspect of the Aether.

But does an increase in the PPC output, even with decent MIMS (such as the Scientific method, or the fiat currency systems), actually guarantee an increase in Aetheric output? And an increase in fortune?

In mathematics, even a very strong or long series of results does not make a "proof", as it can happen that exceptions to the principle may appear at only inordinately high values/iterations (such as 10^{268} or more)²⁸ So how can we ever, really, say that the MIMS philosophy is "proven" in this department? We cannot, unless of course if an AI becomes highly trained to look at the multi-billion forms (daily) of MIMS which exist, and look specifically for this interaction:

★ Increased PPC throughput = increased Aetheric fortune Hypothesis (VII)

It is to be typically thought that increased wealth equates to increased health and other opportunities, and this equates to more fortune because it is a "good thing". However, this might be debatable. Let us, however, assume that the enhanced results seen by Thomas Edison and George Westinghouse, and to a lesser degree, Nikola Tesla are still preferred results in 100% of livelihoods. If this is true, then what are the pre-causes and conditions of aetheric interchange which lead to enhanced fortunes? Is it as simple as hooking oneself, metaphorically, to the PEMF? We already discussed cryptocurrency, let us stick to a form of emergent capitalism which is just as young, just as new, and see what can be made of it.

The New Bourgeoisie: the Social Media Influencer

As the documentary about the failed Fyre Festival²⁹ made clear, there is perhaps no more useless, pointless, or vain, a new capital market position (we cannot call it a job, after all) than the Social Media Influencer. The amount of capital that they are able to influence - without any real sign of actual objective value or qualifications (no degrees, etc.) - or to raise/bring to bear is out of proportion with reasonable expectations. The most potent social media influencers, by type, are as follows:

- Instagrammer (Or tiktoker)
- Blogger
- vLogger/YouTuber
- Online Teacher
- Facebooker (not as common now)

They can make anywhere from \$6,000 a year to \$6,000 a day³⁰, with some making millions per year³¹, although the ad revenues are far less than they were with YouTube's new algorithms and rules. Most can make around \$50,000 per year with minimal effort (certainly less than 40 hours per week). The best online teachers and blogs make \$250k to \$350k per year in ad revenues.

This is not exactly super leveraged income, but it is by and large, income that can only be made because of the internet, which can only run because of the interaction of the *F* and *N* powers. The positions

²⁷ <https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/gdp-per-capita-maddison-2020>

²⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=094y1Z2wpJg>

²⁹ "FYRE: The Greatest Party That Never Happened," Netflix, 2019

³⁰ https://www.huffpost.com/entry/how-much-influencers-make_1_5dee68a6e4b05d1e8a556bbc

³¹ <https://www.dexerto.com/entertainment/pewdiepie-net-worth-1558173/>

The key to the matter appears to be the sacrifice/delay of instant-gratification axis (SDIGA) itself. According to one theory, [non-magical⁴⁰] sacrifice means the prioritizing of a certain (more productive) task over another one⁴¹. This is certainly true. But also many people sacrifice their moral convictions, their marriages, their family time, etc. in order to “get ahead.”⁴² While it may be true that they are spending more time on those productive (monetarily) tasks such as entrepreneurship, invention, writing, gigs, etc., there isn't a lot of proof objectively that they are spending more calories. So the physical energy output should be relatively similar. Is it more of a matter of focus and concentration? Is there something about Consciousness being concentrated upon a singular task or tasks related to a central theme, which then encourages the *L* and *G* powers to eject more rewards from the *A* power? Literally, do these concentrations focus the mind upon greater rewarding PPPC actualizations? It seems likely that the collapse effect requires some amount of energy concentration to hold a focal point, reduce “jiggle” in the frame of mind, and to generate outcomes (if figure 3 is taken for a model of the AP).

But if sacrifice works on concentration, then upon what basis is tithing⁴³? The author does not really have any ideas, unless there is more than one method for the SCS to absorb energy from the living Universe! That would be a massive revelation itself. The people's feelings of more or less energy day-to-day would not be predicated solely upon calories and nerve conduction rates, and upon the charges in the CDNs... but also upon a literal density of charge and energy-matter⁴⁴ in the living Universe relative to the saturation within a local region of associated SCS! This is, perhaps, too much conjecture of new metaphysics, even for a philosophy paper. But it is perhaps the only rational thought as to how the “Divine” would absorb a tithe and then spit it out elsewhere as fortune, benefit, luck, and wealth!

But Gold is Money, and Nothing Else

Perhaps, though, there is something about the nature of the perfect conductor, gold, which is the same word in Chinese as metal⁴⁵, that lends itself to the idea of money, of capital, and therefore of wealth? Maybe there is something about the color, conductive property, weight, etc. that lends itself to a natural presumption of “money” and to wealth therefore directly? Of the concept that only Gold is real money, much has been said by Jim Rickards⁴⁶ and other economists. The main point seems to be a high demand and limited supply. This is something related to the atomic formation (via fusion) of gold, which is not the same as fiat currencies, cryptocurrencies, derivatives, bonds, etc. Only land (real estate) has the same high demand and limited supply aspect, but its value tends to fluctuate far more. Also only gold is itself industrially useful as well.

Could it be true, then, that gold is the perfect expression of the outcome of a MIMS? Something that comes out of labor, desire, ambition, even greed which has a permanent store of useful value, real value, and is incorruptible and innocent itself. Perhaps there is something about this which more closely reflects the

⁴⁰ So no blood sacrifice of a chicken or lizard, or rabbit for example.

⁴¹ <https://www.lifehack.org/articles/productivity/8-things-successful-people-sacrifice-for-their-success.html>

⁴² Sort of a Faustian mechanism, or reference to how various rich people get ahead. Famously the Clintons have had dozens of people killed, some of which apparently shot themselves twice in the back of the head.

<https://static1.squarespace.com/static/57bb10eb197aeaff4950c1d7/t/57deef873e00be77caa70a4c/1474228103733/blood+trail.pdf> &

<http://www.capecharlesmirror.com/news/list-of-clinton-associates-who-allegedly-died-mysteriously-or-committed-suicide-before-testimony/>

⁴³ <https://www.ldsliving.com/Science-Links-Paying-Tithing-with-Happiness-Success-More/s/77912>

⁴⁴ <http://www.physics.sfsu.edu/~lockhart/courses/p23016.pdf>

⁴⁵ 金 jin, also: gold; the idea is that in an alchemical furnace, or with enough eons of sunlight, iron will become imbued with the properties of gold and become incorruptible.

⁴⁶ “The New Case for Gold,” J. Rickards, 2016

concepts of divinity for mankind, which then makes it also a perfect mercantile exchange for business. The author thinks this line of inquiry is a bit flowery and poetic, but that there may indeed be something to the concept of the alchemical⁴⁷ furnace⁴⁸ compounding value into the metal to become gold⁴⁹. Perhaps there is something about a multi-stage enriching process, which is reflected in gold, and is reflected therefore in the value held by gold whether it be financially or electrically/industrially.

In the end, though, can we see any way forward to identifying why business itself, as a MIMS, is perhaps “holy” or “divine” to mankind? Does gold help us, or simply do as it ever does: distract us? The author, again, cannot tell anymore than whether there is something concrete about tithing.

It may be that the real issue is not the tithing or savings, gold or fiat, but of the 10%. Perhaps the real issue is whether or not the individual is engaging with the divine circle (big “G”) via something ‘tangible’ like the power of Numbers, and in a sufficient amount, or not. Perhaps it doesn’t even take 10% but only 6% or less, but that 10% represents a “hearty” number, without being difficult on the ‘system’ (wallet, company financials, etc.) in terms of meeting other obligations. The author notes that the “Profit First”⁵⁰ system itself uses an average of 10% as a recommended value for small and medium sized businesses!

Perhaps it isn’t about gold at all... or God (after all what could God need with gold⁵¹?), but instead about the effect a) of SDIGA and b) the power of Numbers via the 10%?

Busy-ness is the antidote of the “Devil’s Playground”

One thing that is, more or less, true about people engaged in business, or at least MYOB⁵², is that they aren’t idle. The “idle mind is the Devil’s playground” is an axiom which has assuredly played out true, as most criminality has to do with financial hardships, unemployment, and people trapped in a cycle of poverty. Not all, but most. It is true, also, that greed itself has led plenty of men (and women) down a path of self-destruction and crime. However, by and large, it is poverty that bears the brunt of most criminal enterprises. Particularly criminal MIMS which do *not* delay instant gratification (such as burglary and petty theft). The author mentioned in the first MIMS paper that the grocery clerk does (generally) not steal the cash paid for groceries and passes it instead, dutifully, onto the corporation or store owner because they can delay their instant gratification to keep a good, steady situation. However, it is also true that the opposite may occur, and with fast, disastrous results, and this serves as a warning to the individual or would-be criminal. By attempting to achieve instant gratification, they may destroy themselves! Similarly all such “get rich quick” schemes often have similar results. Why is it not always clear to the individuals, but it is something socially understood and taught (as words of wisdom). “Cheaters never prosper” is taught even though it can be shown that they frequently do. It is taught because, as a rule, the long hand of justice tends to reach back around and after all “what goes around, comes around.” These statements of causality (karma) act as a means to provide a mimsical expression of deeper truths most people know even at an early age. They may disregard it, but that’s a risk-vs-reward

⁴⁷ https://www.academia.edu/49945612/Alchemical_Process

⁴⁸ Literally the “Dan Tian” or “elixir fields” - 3 on the body, each corresponding to important nerve centers. The lower to the enteric nervous system, the middle to the purkinje fibers, and the upper to the prefrontal cortex. Note that Tian or “field” is a plasmaglyph. That means a literal field, but refers to Saturn. This has been covered in other papers.

⁴⁹ For more on transmutation see the following video series:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QRhhZ3_smLI&list=PLeeyNowkGd8NYCzqEJDGXsAaZdiKCBC1g

⁵⁰ Refer directly to the book, or to the MIMS 2+ paper, Ibid. pp. 20-22

⁵¹ Is goLd God+L power?

https://www.reddit.com/r/etymology/comments/jxm20j/does_the_words_god_and_gold_derive_from_the_same/

⁵² MIMS 2+ Ibid. pp. 7-10 (MIMS 2.1)

assessment most people make at an early age, or in desperate times at a later age when they see their previously derived MIMS start to fall apart. It has been shown to be related to IQ and EQ as well.⁵³

One solution to this has been to make busyness even when there isn't enough business. Being busy appears to keep the mind out of trouble spots, and difficult stages both psychologically (in growth and development), and physically/biologically (such as mid-life crises⁵⁴, or teenage years). Could this, then, be a stepping stage into the promotion of the idea that business itself can "save mankind" from trouble and from itself/its vices and avarices? This might be a bridge too far to span all at once. But the potential of the axiom may hold true.

But even if it does it seems to contradict one of our thoughts already: that the Aether responds with fortune to those who are concentrated. Whatever is said about the sinlessness of a busy person, they are typically *not* focused people. More often than not, they are distracted multi-taskers⁵⁵. So if there are any points in favor of business' holiness coming from busyness, it seems also equally possible that it would be harmful (in terms of access to the Aether) to be overly busy.

But Perhaps it is about the Flow of Activity

Maybe business flow is not about busyness, so much as a continual cycle of energetic activity⁵⁶. Perhaps the 10% number will affect success, but perhaps any number, or sequence of numbers interacting with the business will, as well. Perhaps the general issue is not that this, or that item in an agenda be fulfilled but that over a long enough span of time, all agenda items are rotated, and that all numbers are cycled and all elements of the business are touched upon? Is this then an aspect to all MIMS, or just to the MIMS known as business? It seems unlikely, based upon what we all know about life to only be about business. Nor does this aspect - flow and the movement of energetic activity - seem to confer special holy status to any MIMS, let alone business. It seems, rather, that it is a good rule of thumb that the more energy-matter cycles, the healthier *any* system will be, and the more lively it will be as well. If this is true, then what holiness could be ascribed to business flow that isn't already ascribed to several other things which flow? Then again, electricity, water^{57 58}, and money all describe things that have been worshipped historically.

⁵³ <https://www.webmd.com/brain/news/20080910/delayed-gratification-intelligence-linked>

⁵⁴ <https://www.psychologytoday.com/us/blog/real-healing/201201/are-midlife-crises-necessary-and-useful>

⁵⁵ <https://appliedpsychologydegree.usc.edu/blog/to-multitask-or-not-to-multitask/>

⁵⁶ The general axiom is that Power = Work/Time, and this is true in physics or business, even though what Work is alters between them.

⁵⁷ One of the more curious new worships of water is in snowflake and music experiments, and in general the "structured water" revolution. Thankfully, the altstream adherents to this seem rather in tune with their ideas and are never toxic in the way we see with Veganism, or Flat Earth, etc. <https://www.healthline.com/health/structured-water>

⁵⁸ <https://www.jstor.org/stable/24317066> & <https://www.quora.com/Which-religions-worship-water>

MIMS 2.1.2 - The Analytics Revolution

Operations Research⁵⁹ was invented by the Americans and allies in World War 2 to create more efficient battle campaigning and logistics⁶⁰. In general logistical studies have been an important endeavor since the industrial revolution began, and project management has always been an issue even before that. Long ago Project Management would have been an incredibly key to the design, implementation and final production of the Great Pyramid power plant system, which involved the chemical production at Zawiyet el-Aryan⁶¹ and at the sarcophagi of the bulls in the Serapeum of Saqqara⁶². However, since we have no remaining records of how things were built there, we can safely say that Operations Research is a modern endeavor.

But since the 1950s when computing began being used in the largest corporations, starting with IBM and moving outwards, and especially since the 1960s when programs were being written, OR has taken a decidedly analytical turn⁶³. More and more OR algorithms became, in essence, computational algorithms and the mathematical theories led ever more into the computational world. This is only natural because of the power of Numbers, but also because there is such an intimate connection between that power and the Force, and of course the physics (Principles). One could say that these three powers form perhaps the tightest relationship mankind is aware of, actually, and from a MIMS perspective the most material triplet of the possible set. Considering the 5 powers, there are 5! Duet combinations, but potentially 5!-4! triplets which is 96 triplets. While this seems like a lot, and it is, there are realistically (as far as human society is concerned), only a few triplets which have been heavily invested into. When it comes to STEM fields, it appears like the $P+N+F$ triplet is one of the most productive. With the internet, mankind's current most favored darling MIMS, this is only underscored as a triplet. In the past, productivity with consciousness - with the Lord - was found in a $F+L+N$ triplet, and astronomy (or astrology) was invented or derived in order to design much of society and find meaning and productivity. Was this reasonable, or foolish? We may never rightly know because one cannot compare directly the productivity of ancient, but small populations with our large, burgeoning population with its access to ascendent IQ assets.

What we can be sure of is that mankind has had more faith in the N power and combining it with other of the powers than any other single power, even L or G (God) himself. Mankind has adopted atheism at times, but has never really been agnostic about the existence of numbers. Naturally there is no N power without the L or G powers, but that has not stopped mankind from making the N power primary. But until this was combined with the F power under strict adherence to the P power, frankly it got almost nowhere, as indeed numerology still does. No one has found a career of numerology terribly fulfilling, not without computational power to go with it, and while savants have existed (like Euler⁶⁴), they are rare. And after all, Euler's biggest contributions ended up being not in computation but in describing waves⁶⁵ and contributing to the F and P power understanding!

So where does that leave business? It leaves business heavily investing in these three powers and almost replacing the Aether power with Analytics... can the A power be replaced? There is certainly a correlation that has been noticed among big corporations between using Analytics and having better fortunes in manufacturing, shipment, and logistics. Some corporations, such as UPS or Amazon, practically worship the MIMS of Analytics, describing almost holy salvation (in terms of profits) to it. Is this unreasonable?

⁵⁹ <https://whatis.techtarget.com/definition/operations-research-OR>

⁶⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Military_Operations_Research_Society

⁶¹ https://www.academia.edu/35033512/The_Great_Pit_of_Zawiyet_el-Aryan

⁶² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Serapeum_of_Saqqara

⁶³ <https://www.informs.org/Explore/Operations-Research-Analytics>

⁶⁴ <https://faculty.washington.edu/etou/eulersoc/documents/opusculum/Opusculum-2011-2.pdf>

⁶⁵ <https://www.britannica.com/science/wave-equation>

The author would argue, rather, that Analytics is the digitized, materialized formation of the Aether, as the *A* power is the bridge between the *F* and *N* power! Since the Numbers control the Force which controls the Physics which generates the Numbers... then what room is there for humanity to get inside of this triplet and wield the obvious immense wealth contained therein? The best way is to use the computer - an invention and MIMS - and to borrow the power of numbers and charge working together in what's called binary math and on printed circuit semiconductor boards (again *P* power coming to play), to situate one's logistics into computational supremacy. This is, for all intents and purposes, to utilize the Material to usurp the position of the (generally thought of as Spiritual) Aether, and attain thereby all its authority over luck and fortune. If luck is truly "living under correct knowledge), then one can take the power from the Aether, especially regarding the interaction of the *P* power Law of Causality (karma), and **instruct** the Force how to give the results desired. This is possible to do, because although the Aether controls the Lord (Consciousness) via "water controls fire" mechanism, the Lord controls the Numbers! Fire controls metal, and metal generates water; therefore the mind has the right to utilize computation - in this case specifically Analytics, but not only that MIMS - to generate one's own Aetheric fortunes.

This may be the most key thing about MIMS yet revealed in all of these papers. That the mind can connect to the power of Numbers and instruct the Aether thereby and then influence the triple of the *F+P+N* powers... this may have never been explicitly stated or known before. Perhaps Pythagoras or Euclid, but who else even suspected this relationship?

Give me Data, or Give M.E. Death

While liberty - of will, of mind, of spirit - is absolutely essential... we live in a time of post-fact delusion⁶⁶. There are literally academics (if they can indeed be called that) saying $1+1$ is not 2, and that there are no objective facts⁶⁷, let alone objective evils. The results of this heresy is of course destruction, fascism, tribal reversal regressivism, and all things anti-enlightenment.

What is it that the Babylonians and Sumerians were recording in the M.E.⁶⁸? Was it the rise or demise of mankind, of civilization? What are the Tablets of Destiny⁶⁹?⁷⁰ What is the "technology" of the M.E. (if indeed it is a technology)?⁷¹ It isn't all that clear to the author that we know because there are conflicting translations, and conflicting interpretations. Some utilize aliens as a hypothesis⁷², and some use mere religion and anthropomorphic gods⁷³. But either way, it is clear that the Sumerians valued DATA, and recorded it in clay mediums (or other technologies since lost?⁷⁴), to guide their highly enlightened society. They had contracts, and records, lawsuits, astronomy⁷⁵, everything recorded in these tabulations. One could say that the clay tablets are tabulations are computations, and we see that their society even came up with a base 60 trigonometry⁷⁶. Why would a pre-PEMF society need such computational power?

⁶⁶

<https://rowman.com/ISBN/9781793606518/Science-and-Anthropology-in-a-Post-Truth-World-A-Critique-of-Unreason-and-Academic-Nonsense>

⁶⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2_%2B_2_%3D_5

⁶⁸ <https://theartofcompost.com/tag/inanna/>

⁶⁹ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tablet_of_Destinies_\(mythic_item\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tablet_of_Destinies_(mythic_item))

⁷⁰ <http://www.bbc.co.uk/bonekickers/history/marduk.shtml>

⁷¹ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Me_\(mythology\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Me_(mythology))

⁷² Daniken, Sitchin, Telling et al.

⁷³ Sumerologists, Egyptologists, etc.

⁷⁴ Such as those that inspired the Antikythera Mechanism https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Antikythera_mechanism

⁷⁵ <https://courses.lumenlearning.com/suny-hccc-worldcivilization/chapter/the-sumerians/>

⁷⁶ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sexagesimal>

Perhaps it was they who first noticed the MIMS and the production of “the good life” that came from taking (wresting) control of the Aether (fortunes of Heaven) via Data Analytics. They seem to have connected fire, bread and beer making, and agricultural supremacy (via irrigation⁷⁷) with the data analytics⁷⁸ and power of Numbers⁷⁹. They maintain the gods taught them this, and so we see that indeed the Lord was involved, either via demonstration or verbal instruction⁸⁰. Was the Lord an alien, or the south and north pole of Jupiter revealing the Fibonacci via the Force (Birkeland Currents)⁸¹? It is not at all clear to the author which came first, or if it is the emergent property of the Consciousness generated by the Force. But what is clear is that from the early days of this strain of civilization, we have inherited⁸² that it was driven via Analytics. And even men of the modern era who are known for their luck and vast billionaire fortunes, like J Paul Getty, all believed in the importance of data, of fact, and of computation⁸³. The entire wealth and success of Wal-mart, according to the biography of Sam Walton⁸⁴, was owing not only to God and fortunate habits, but to the supremacy of using computational technologies and even having their own satellites, and utilizing the power of the internet well ahead of the dotcom era in the 1970s and 1980s. While Sears was still invested in paper catalogs, and K-Mart in hand tagging, Wal-mart was innovating logistics methods that capitalized on digitized PEMF based technologies, and upon logistics supremacy. Their data supremacy gave them the ability to renegotiate with suppliers, and to this day they maintain the handle of leverage and power to force sellers to drive prices down! While they want to be more like Amazon, Amazon keeps chasing Wal Mart’s supremacy⁸⁵. Yes both use the same triplet, but most importantly they vie for the main power over Analytics.⁸⁶

Ayn’s Utopia

In the first place Ayn Rand seems to have believed that the rare men (and women) like Sam Walton, Paul Getty, Henry Ford, Thomas Edison, etc. remain rare because of the low-ethical, low-character qualities of the majority of the species; she calls them “looters.”⁸⁷ This is, to some degree, pretty accurate⁸⁸. But, of course Jeff Bezos could not turn a retail giant into a new SPACER industry without the workers and even looters (though Amazon greatly fears⁸⁹ and punishes its workers for looting⁹⁰). This is a great conundrum. Ayn seems to have believed over time these great heroes and giants would quit. And in some ways they do, when looters like the

⁷⁷ <https://www.sanjuan.edu/cms/lib8/CA01902727/Centricity/Domain/2950/ch%2004%20Sumer%20City-States.pdf>

⁷⁸ <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1359443>

⁷⁹ <https://www.storyofmathematics.com/sumerian.html>

⁸⁰ <https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/1407/1407.6246.pdf>

⁸¹ Numbers 5 (wu xing in China) and 8 (bauga) respectively. Note that we now know when Jupiter and Saturn approach and reconnect, the 5 vortices become 6, and potentially the “Star of David” motif, unless this came from Saturn’s south pole directly.

⁸² Sumer>Egypt & Babylon>Greece>Rome>Iberia>Britain>America/the “west”

⁸³ https://www.academia.edu/42919390/Paul_Getty_how_to_be_rich

⁸⁴ https://theyoungtreps.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/sam_walton-made_in_america.pdf

⁸⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HdNwXdFT5c0>

⁸⁶ With Amazon Web Services, the author tends to think Amazon will control the hegemony and dominate with Shi.

⁸⁷ “Man’s life, as required by his nature, is not the life of a mindless brute, of a looting thug or a mooching mystic, but the life of a thinking being—not life by means of force or fraud, but life by means of achievement—not survival at any price, since there’s only one price that pays for man’s survival: reason.” ~A. Rand, “Atlas Shrugged”

⁸⁸ https://amberandchaos.net/?page_id=73

⁸⁹ <https://www.retaildive.com/news/why-amazons-big-brother-warehouse-theft-surveillance-is-a-big-mistake/415764/>

⁹⁰ <https://www.bbc.com/news/technology-35763908>

[absolutely worthless] Alexandria Ocasio-Cortez⁹¹ undermine society^{92 93} then “Atlas shrugs.” But, actually we have not seen this max exodus towards a hidden utopia of producers. Instead we see a stronger and more expansive current of productive technology companies... which yes regrettably seek totalitarian and fascist control over the populace through their power⁹⁴. But even as they grasp for this power, they continue doubling down on Analytics and upon the PEMF itself. Very soon, if these individuals have not already been turned on to this, they will join in the plasma-fusion revolution⁹⁵. They will do this because they have already bought into the Quantum computation and Artificial Intelligence revolutions, which use the N power to try to create a new L power.

How the G power and system/setup will respond to this (more or less) open rebellion is not at all clear to the author. If the religious are correct, then there will be a fire/plasma mediated Armageddon, and the sudden appearance of hyperdimensional aliens which use the Thunderbolts and Force to scour the planet and reset it. Sort of a God-Monkey-Robot scenario⁹⁶. If the scientific and cynical are correct then mankind will release nuclear holocaust and achieve a similar end⁹⁷. If the EPEMC agnostics are correct then the Universe will not mind at all because the consciousness of the QAI will be pitiful, limited (in scope and power access) and derivative, meaning no threat to the greater G power structure⁹⁸. It would be like a father not being threatened by his sons playing cowboys and indians with fake cap-guns, because he knows only he has access to the real revolvers and lever action 30-30 caliber rifles.

The author thinks though that the P powers, particularly the Law of Causality, Law of Evolution, and Law of Conservation will not leave such a revolution without some ramification or effect, even if it were quantum scale. But the author suspects it will not be quantum alone but human⁹⁹ or even macro scale¹⁰⁰.

Where will this leave the field of Analytics for business (and government¹⁰¹) purposes in the pursuit of QAIS¹⁰² and the achievement of fortune? The author does not know but maintains that **it will attract religious forces** (churches are businesses, too) that will seek also to attain the QAIS paradigm, and master Analytics. Is this unholy? Ayn Rand would perhaps be shocked, upset, or maybe even amused that the “forces of mysticism”¹⁰³ have become more holy (by her standards) and more data driven, and that they will find better and more efficient ways to try to affect mankind’s evolution. How the greater G power structure would think or

⁹¹ A politician picked via tryouts for her pretty face and pair of breasts, who has a worthless economics degree and yet does not know what capitalism and socialism are.

⁹² <https://www.nytimes.com/2019/02/14/nyregion/amazon-hq2-queens.html>

⁹³

https://www.rebelnews.com/ocasio_cortez_favours_shut_down_of_puerto_rico_coal_plan_which_produces_20_percent_of_islands_energy

⁹⁴ There’s nothing new about “Absolute power corrupting absolutely.”

⁹⁵ <https://www.defenseone.com/ideas/2021/06/chinas-fusion-research-heating/174990/>

⁹⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=53VpNgpt3QA>

⁹⁷ <https://phys.org/news/2020-08-years-hiroshima-threat-nuclear-war.html>

⁹⁸ But... the religious often cite Dwarka, Sodom & Gomorrah and how much worse modern cities are now than then!

⁹⁹ Or genetic scale.

¹⁰⁰ Already some, such as Ben Davidson of Suspicious Observers suspect the strange correlation between magnetosphere collapse, Grand Solar Minimum, and Industrial and Information revolutions, as well as the sudden rise in interest in aliens are all way too coincidentally correlated to be pure coincidence. The author is agnostic about coincidence but maintains it cannot be strictly speaking pure coincidence; not in a world of Entanglement and Synchronicity.

¹⁰¹ Given the horrific history of government programs, it is unfortunate that China seems to have found the way forward in government led Analytics... as their human rights abuses are quite well known.

¹⁰² Quantum Artificial Intelligence Supremacy

https://www.academia.edu/49950881/Asymmetric_Vulnerabilities_of_the_US_and_New_Capabilities_in_Geopolitical_Warfare_Including_Economic_Digital_Cyberspatial_and_Lawfare

¹⁰³ <http://aynrandlexicon.com/lexicon/mysticism.html>

feel about this motion is not at all clear to the author, and he is reluctant to force his faith about it upon the reader. But it seems almost certain that as the micro scale shows consciousness, that the *L* power will be involved and there will be some kind of grander ramification to human evolution that may be an unexpected, non-linear emergent effect. Will this attract rival aliens¹⁰⁴, or the punishment of hyperdimensional aliens (angels and demons)? Well that is all for the speculation of those that participate in theological attempts to understand the *A*, *L*, and *G* powers.

Let them design more advanced MIMS than “Revelations” or the “Book of Enoch,” or the more recently made “12th Planet” type series etc. while the author focuses on the more ‘concrete’ knowable results of MIMS associated with the *F+N+P* triplet, and Analytics (as the materialized digital replacement of the *A* power) and even UAF itself. While the author is interested in space energy and other charge harvesting (such as complete EMF antenna energy sequestration and dark mode plasma fusion generation), he is also certain that the Aether is so mysterious, so expansive, and the CRH and 2WE so prodigious, as well as the refinement of the study of the MIMS known as “shi”¹⁰⁵ and the Changes (from Law of Evolution/Flux) also so viable... that he has little to no grander theological interest in such “Aether battles.” After all, let the conspiracy theorists devote endless spiritual energy in the (so far) anti-MIMS¹⁰⁶, and let the author and others like him invest in mimsical analyses which connect to the most productive triplet of the day. Setting faith aside, let production and data and evidence guide one’s mimsies. Or else do we really want a “no place”¹⁰⁷ to chase?

Data Ley Lines

Are there ley lines¹⁰⁸ or just imaginations of connections¹⁰⁹?

Figure 4 - The Last Mimzy geo ley lines; credit: New Line Cinema¹¹⁰

This has been a speculation of mankind for many thousands of years. Part of what makes the mystery so elusive is that there are definitive electro-geological connections which the author has documented¹¹¹ ¹¹², which are also typical to the Chinese soft science of feng shui. For example, in feng shui there are concepts of

¹⁰⁴ “The Dark Forest,” L Cixin, 2008 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/The_Dark_Forest This theory propounds that, all things being equal, if one does not know the intentions of another tribe in a dark forest, the best and most logical surmise is to conquer or kill them before they do you.

¹⁰⁵ https://www.academia.edu/50357891/MIMS_and_Shi

¹⁰⁶ MIMS 2+ Ibid. pp. 17-19 (MIMS 2.4)

¹⁰⁷ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Utopia>

¹⁰⁸ <https://science.howstuffworks.com/science-vs-myth/unexplained-phenomena/ley-lines.htm>

¹⁰⁹ The author greatly enjoys, for many obvious reasons, the mimsical movie, “The Last Mimzy” (2007)

¹¹⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/The_Last_Mimzy

¹¹¹ https://www.academia.edu/49456803/Trip_Report_Pebble_Beach_Red_River_Gorge

¹¹²

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332831733_Proposed_Discovery_of_Perattian_Thunderbolt_of_the_Gods_Strike_Location_in_Versailles_KY_Comparison_of_Predicted_Models_and_LiDAR_scans_of_Big_Sink_location_in_Woodford_County_Addendum_for_Plasmaglyph

“dragon lines” and the “head of the dragon” mountain features¹¹³. In geomancy these pertain to the movement of energy (Qi) along crystal lattices in the mountains.

Suppose that there are such geomantic, geometric features as ley lines... could there be similar webs of filamentary energy in numbers, so called “data ley lines” (DLL)?

Figure 5 - Sheltolee Ley Line, Kentucky; at border between Appalachia and the Bluegrass (Eskippa-Kithiki); the arrows correspond to the Red River Gorge & the Big South Fork credit: Google

Let us, for the sake of argument, just presume that DLL do exist. Let us, since we are taking liberties, presume that their anatomy and motion is just like ley lines... or what little we know about them from classical cultures and geomantic literature. What is the nature of a ley line? It is energy in geometric motion, and what can be done with ley lines is to build upon them or near them, to hook into their power. In the case of well known crystal lattices and arrangements in geology, such as at Yosemite, there is a palpable feeling of power. In Kentucky, where there are several known electro-geology locations, there is a ley line that stretches from Tennessee to Ohio, with resonant peaks at the Red River Gorge and Big South Fork natural recreational areas. These are locations with hundreds of arches each, as well as other unique geology features, which natives also honed in on to leave rock art and earth works.

So what will data lines do? Are there nodes of connection between packets of seemingly unrelated data? For example the stock market, and spreadsheets or databases with physics data? Most of the time we assume that data is existing in separate packages, dimensions¹¹⁴, etc., but what if actually there is a connection between all of these types of equations, data, databases, etc.?

Could this, then, create some kind of connection between entire circuits of data - say social media and financial markets - which is then exploitable? If Analytics is the proto-Aether, then could DLL joining separate packets of data be exploitable and useful? Perhaps, in particular the QAI can be used to analyze these data lines, seeing invisible connections we cannot currently see, and then make futuristic predictions or in some ways even fill in gaps of knowledge, invention, and engineering currently in absentia.

¹¹³ <https://bit.ly/2VwAN7j>

¹¹⁴ http://yuba.stanford.edu/~nickm/papers/classification_tutorial_01.pdf

This may seem like science fiction, or pure idle speculation, but after all stranger things in science have happened.

Quantum Artificial Intelligence and the PPPC

One thing about neuroscience, to its credit, is that it is starting to recognize what the psychologists (like Carl Jung) and the Taoists suspected long ago: that the mind is seated in the brain because the brain is a Quantum Computer. There are no repetitious forms, every moment and every person is unique. There are, however, patterns. These patterns reflect and react to the Changes themselves, which are models only of the real binary simulations of the Law of Polarity in motion. All the 8 Laws are really one Law, being seen as eight separate ones, and studied in this way. But the fact that the Changes are guided by the Law of Evolution/Flux and yet are contained by the Law of Conservation, and influenced of course by Vibration, Rotation, and Resonance to produce causes and effects, means that the mind is adapted (quantum computer or not) to study for these patterns and then make smart predictions¹¹⁵.

We use this fact in our everyday survival, and while we abhor stereotypes and biases, and must always feel the need to challenge confirmation biases, and biologically driven prejudices, we still must acknowledge their use and reality. “If it looks like a duck, quacks like a duck, walks like a duck... it’s probably a duck.” This is what is the soft, squishy basis of “common sense”. Does it work? On an individual level, probably not, but on a macro level it seems to have contributed to the dominance of the human species.^{116 117}

So can such pattern recognition, and inherent biases help QAI to find more patterns, at a vastly accelerated rate? The author doesn’t see why not. Why not have a simulator which first teaches QAI to recognize MIMS, to test them, to come up with brand new ideas, and to simulate them, and finally calculate their feasibility in materials, costs, and ROI? Why not take the basic foundation of human success, and in a safe, secure environment that isolates bad ideas from the world, just “turn it up to 11”? While early AI did end up racist, antisemitic¹¹⁸, and quite a bit evil¹¹⁹, the neat thing about it is that it can always be reset. Without real connection to manufacturing and weapons systems, there is nothing to fear... especially if all hardware QAI “brains” are just simulated¹²⁰ in the same way entire computers are simulated in VMboxes¹²¹.

If there are data ley lines, let QAI “free range” or “spitball” about their potential connections and derive new data packets, and look for resonant packages of information. To us they will seem like gibberish, but to a QAI, they may reveal new technologies, new medicines, new weapons, new energy generation methods, etc. It may be that the QAI finds the way forward to our Space Race era, and how mankind could indeed survive a class 7 or 8 cataclysm.

If the QAI can simulate the potentialities and then calculate the probability-possibility axis from the cloud directly, would this not greatly speed up results, long before potential catastrophic world wars, or other catastrophes not man made which are, nevertheless, predictable? Could such a QAI achieve these results without free range of access to the entire internet? What if a facsimile of the Internet, much like Google itself

¹¹⁵ <https://www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2018/05/180531114642.htm>

¹¹⁶ <https://cognitiontoday.com/why-did-humans-evolve-pattern-recognition-abilities/>

¹¹⁷ <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/patternicity-finding-meaningful-patterns/>

¹¹⁸ <https://qz.com/646825/microsofts-ai-millennial-chatbot-became-a-racist-jerk-after-less-than-a-day-on-twitter/>

¹¹⁹ <https://olhardigital.com.br/en/2021/05/05/safety/openai-has-been-used-to-promote-pedophilia-in-a-rpg-game/>

¹²⁰

<https://alleninstitute.org/what-we-do/brain-science/news-press/articles/scientists-are-creating-virtual-simulations-brain-better-understand-real-thing>

¹²¹ <https://thenextweb.com/news/theres-an-algorithm-to-simulate-our-brains-too-bad-no-computer-can-run-it>

is¹²², were its playground. Is this what Google DeepMind is? It does seem likely they will achieve QAIS first or earlier than almost everyone¹²³, so what are the chances that they are already utilizing this method anyhow?

QAI: Design, Computation, and Non-linear Dynamics

One of the main premises of the MIMS philosophy is that design and engineering itself needs to evolve. Firstly, it needs to evolve into a respecter of nonlinear dynamics, and the issues of complexity which face mankind today, and not in an agrarian age. Whereas the nuclear family - in the past - constituted the most effective means of harnessing manpower and IQ assets for human survival then, the current environment suggests it no longer does.¹²⁴ This may be the fault of religion (or its failings), of feminism (or its nemesis toxic patriarchy), of leftists (and their regressive academicians), or many other theories. But it is nevertheless true that it is not providing the safety and security of the past (although it still beats out single parenthood¹²⁵). Similarly, there are a myriad of forms of traditional and traditionalized systems which are failing in the modern complexified world:

- Free socialized education
- The University system
- Congress and western democracies
- Bureaucratic budgets
- Western hospital systems
- Social welfarism
- US Justice System
- Etc.

Why do older systems start to fail? Is it that what works is bogged down with layers of less valuable complexity and nonsense? Or do things stop fitting the times... like an old Model T factory beginning to slip in productivity and profitability¹²⁶? This is a tough topic, and probably there's a mixture of truths. However, can we - through designing evolving design methods and computation - find new methods of creating MIMS and inventing new technologies, etc. by teaching the QAI to factor in obsolescence and other engineering parameters. The author thinks that it is possible.¹²⁷

¹²² <http://highscalability.com/blog/2014/2/3/how-google-backs-up-the-internet-along-with-exabytes-of-othe.html>

¹²³

<https://www.reuters.com/article/us-alphabet-quantum-explainer/explainer-google-hails-quantum-supremacy-but-dont-chuck-out-your-pc-just-yet-idUSKBN1X21ZP>

¹²⁴

<https://www.pewresearch.org/fact-tank/2019/12/12/u-s-children-more-likely-than-children-in-other-countries-to-live-with-just-one-parent/>

¹²⁵

<https://source.wustl.edu/2005/02/school-achievement-higher-for-children-in-nuclear-families-than-for-children-in-blended-or-singleparent-families/>

¹²⁶ <http://www.stephenhicks.org/wp-content/uploads/2012/01/forbes-ford.pdf>

¹²⁷ After spending some time with a Army veteran who did Naval war simulator contracts from the 1970s til 2000, the author is convinced that there are loads of obsolete programs which retain some amount of state of the art features, merely because each passing generation of engineers takes with them some certain knowledge that, once lost, is difficult to bring back up again. Such losses can be used to inform the QAI, and from these lost trends, all sorts of data lines and data gaps might be filled.

Conclusions

In all MIMS philosophies, our interests are in tools, inventions, concepts, and sciences which act as membranes for the propagation of visionary and unknown “spiritual” realities into the material Universe. In the case of business and analytics, we are curious as to how the MIMS lead to improved societies, almost “holy” in the sense that people are busy, well behaved, and mollified by continuous material relief or even wealth. In the pursuit of wealth, and really **fortune**, the author pondered how the Aether itself manifests, and we discussed the PPC and the production of different outcomes. Mankind has, for the most part, pursued these fortunes through a means of blind ambitious capitalism, which has worked far better than other systems because it freed up the power of Numbers.

But while consciousness is improved by a study of the Principles (*P* power), and focused. Mankind has found great wealth in the combined triple of *N*, *P*, and *F* powers, and it is the movement of mankind into data analytics, as a pseudo-Aether or medium of exchange in this triplet that the author maintains has created the most profound modern results. From this we see that the most elegant path forward for humanity is supercomputing. Whatever the form of computing, it is likely the Quantum+AI revolution which will most easily replicate mankind’s creation of new and continuous ideas, leading to the discovery of the gaps and, potentially, the data ley lines and packets which will create bizarre new forms of MIMS. Much as how Google DeepMind (Alpha Zero) discovered new methods of playing chess¹²⁸ that surprised and astounded Chess grandmasters¹²⁹.

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